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Psychological Distress as Predictor of Academic Motivation and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School Students

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Abstract.

This study explores the psychological distress, academic motivation, and dropout intentions of Senior High School students in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) at San Emmanuel National High School. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study aimed to examine the levels of depression, anxiety, and stress among ALS students and their relationships with academic motivation and dropout intentions. Data were collected through standardized questionnaires: the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21), the Academic Motivation Scale (AMS-HS 28), and the Course Dropout Intention Scale. Findings revealed that ALS students exhibited moderate to extremely severe levels of psychological distress, particularly in terms of anxiety, while maintaining high levels of academic motivation. Depression showed a significant positive correlation with motivation, suggesting that higher motivation levels are linked to greater depressive symptoms, possibly due to academic pressures. However, no significant relationships were found between anxiety or stress and academic motivation, nor between psychological distress and dropout intentions. Despite experiencing significant psychological distress, students generally showed low intentions to drop out, with most reporting a strong commitment to completing their education. The results underscore the need for comprehensive mental health support within the ALS framework, including counseling and motivation-enhancing interventions, to foster both emotional well-being and academic success. Recommendations include expanding the Psychological First Aid program to address the mental health needs of ALS learners more effectively and provide targeted support to those struggling with depressive symptoms and academic pressures.

Keywords: Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, Dropout Intentions, Alternative Learning System (ALS), Mental Health Support

1.0 Introduction

ALS Senior High School students face a range of psychological challenges that may influence their academic engagement and intentions to stay in school. Previous research underscores that psychological distress is a powerful predictor of learning outcomes (Bauya et al., 2022), affecting students' motivation (Rasoaisi, 2017), performance (Tuastumban & Naparota, 2025), and choices about continuing their education. However, the connections among these variables in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) Senior High School (SHS) remain underexplored.

Anxiety and depression are global mental health concerns that significantly affect individuals, particularly university students, who often face numerous stressors during their academic journey (Kandasamy et al., 2025). The World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the importance of addressing mental health as a critical component of overall health, establishing an action plan for 2013–2030 to promote the prevention, treatment, and recovery from mental health disorders (World Health Organization, 2013).

Mental health issues such as anxiety, stress, and depression are widespread among university students globally. Studies report that up to 67% experience moderate anxiety, 52% stress, and 41% depression symptoms (Nakie et al., 2022), with similar rates observed in Ethiopia and worldwide (Lemma et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2017; Salem et al., 2016). These conditions often impair academic performance and well-being, underscoring the urgent need for improved campus mental health support and intervention (Baryannis et al., 2022).

Alternative Learning System (ALS) participants face strong social stigma, often being perceived as academic failures or second-chance learners, which damages their self-esteem and motivation (Reyeset al., 2021). This stigma, combined with insufficient community and parental engagement, undermines student motivation and retention, as many ALS learners lack essential encouragement and support for sustained educational success (Bautista & Palisoc, 2022). These challenges contribute to the complex barriers ALS students face in achieving academic and personal growth, highlighting the need for increased awareness, community involvement, and supportive policies to improve ALS outcomes.

It is notable that psychological distress significantly impacts academic motivation and retention among students. However, the specific interplay of depression, anxiety, and stress with motivation and dropout intentions remains understudied within the Alternative Learning System (ALS) Senior High School context. While global research highlights these mental health issues among university populations, ALS learners face unique challenges, including strong social stigma and limited community support. Hence, determining the current mental health status of ALS students is essential to tailor effective interventions that support their academic engagement and overall well-being.

Thus, this study aimed to determine and correlate the levels of Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, and Dropout Intentions among ALS students of San Emmanuel National High School to understand their interrelationships and their impact on students' educational outcomes. Specifically, the research sought to quantify the extent of depression, anxiety, and stress experienced by learners and how these psychological distress factors relate to their motivation toward academic pursuits. The study's results served as the basis for enhancing the Psychological First Aid program at ALS Senior High School.

This study aimed to determine and correlate the Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, and Dropout Intentions of ALS students at San Emmanuel National High School during the academic year 2025-2026. The study's results served as the basis for enhancing the Psychological First Aid program at ALS Senior High School.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Psychological Distress of ALS Senior High School Students in terms of:
 - 1.1 depression;
 - 1.2 anxiety; and
 - 1.3 stress?
2. What is the level of Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School students?
3. What is the level of Dropout Intention among ALS Senior High School students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the Psychological Distress and Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the Psychological Distress and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School students?
6. Based on the study, what intervention program can be developed?

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Method

A descriptive-correlational research design determined potentially significant relationships that may subsequently be used to formulate causal links (Brown, 2005, as cited in Cwiękała-Lewis, 2019). In this study, the Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School of San Emmanuel National High School were measured and correlated to establish the grounds for the enhanced Psychological First-Aid initiative of the school.

2.2 Participants and Other Sources of Data Information

Generally, the respondents of the study were the ALS Senior High School students at San Emmanuel National High School. Specifically, the study adhered to the following inclusion criteria to

identify the respondents: A respondent must be (1) a bona fide student at San Emmanuel National High School and (2) willing to participate.

2.3 Data Gathering Methods

Formal permissions were secured from the San Emmanuel National High School administration before the administration. To gather the necessary data, the researchers administered a questionnaire that included the DASS-21 by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995), the Academic Motivation Scale (AMS-HS 28) by Vallerand et al. (1993), and the Course Dropout Intention Scale by Yupanqui-Lorenzo et al. (2023). The test was conducted face-to-face in classroom settings under standardized procedures to ensure fairness, consistency, and minimal distractions.

Ethical research standards were observed throughout the process, including properly citing adapted tools and acknowledging original authors in compliance with the American Psychological Association’s general research ethics guidelines. The DASS-21, AMS-HS 28, and Course Dropout Intention Scale were administered and analyzed to determine the psychological distress, academic motivation, and dropout intentions of ALS senior high school students. The data was then tabulated for interpretation.

2.4 Statistical Treatment

The study gathered the necessary data by determining the levels of Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, and Dropout Intentions among San Emmanuel National High School ALS SHS students, as well as their correlations. Thus, descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the study.

In descriptive statistics, feature identification and parameter estimation are obtained with minimal assumptions on the underlying population (Selvamuthu & Das, 2018, as cited in Fegarido & Horno, 2025). More specifically, for SOP 1, scoring formulas or algorithms for the DASS-21 (Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21) were used to compute the data gathered. They serve as subscale computation formulas used to calculate the total scores for Depression, Anxiety, and Stress from the questionnaire, which are then scaled (multiplied by 2) to align with severity ranges for interpretation.

For SOPs two and three, the measure of central tendency is the mean, which is most appropriately used for continuous data, such as variables measured on a constant, uninterrupted scale that can take any value on that scale (Turner, 2013).

On the other hand, inferential statistics were used for SOPs 4 and 5 to determine the significant relationships among respondents’ psychological stress, academic motivation, and dropout intentions. According to Taherdoost (2020), inferential analysis uses a small sample to conclude a larger population. Specifically, Pearson’s *r* correlation was used for SOPs 4 and 5 to determine whether there is a significant relationship among the Psychological Distress, Academic Motivation, and Dropout Intentions of the ALS learners.

For SOP six, the researcher identified the implications of the study’s results. It was then used as the basis for the proposed enhancement of the Psychological First Aid Program in the ALS Senior High School Program at San Emmanuel National High School.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This section presents the visual presentation, the textual description of the computed data, and the implications of the findings from the gathered data.

Table 1. Level of Psychological Distress of ALS Senior High School Students in Terms of Depression

Code	Depression	Total	Count
1	7	14	Moderate
2	10	20	Moderate
3	7	14	Moderate

Table 1 (continued). *Level of Psychological Distress of ALS Senior High School Students in Terms of Depression*

Code	Depression	Total	Count
4	10	20	Moderate
5	12	24	Severe
6	16	32	Extremely Severe
7	15	30	Extremely Severe
8	11	22	Severe
9	10	20	Moderate
10	7	14	Moderate
11	8	16	Moderate
12	9	18	Moderate
13	14	28	Extremely Severe
14	6	12	Mild
15	12	24	Severe
16	5	10	Mild
17	2	4	Normal
18	11	22	Severe
19	18	36	Extremely Severe
20	8	16	Moderate
21	7	14	Moderate
22	8	16	Moderate
23	9	18	Moderate
24	14	28	Extremely Severe
25	12	24	Severe
26	3	6	Normal
27	5	10	Mild
28	12	24	Severe
29	7	14	Moderate
30	9	18	Moderate
31	9	18	Moderate
32	6	12	Mild
33	3	6	Normal
34	6	12	Mild
35	10	20	Moderate
36	10	20	Moderate
37	9	18	Moderate
38	16	32	Extremely Severe
39	12	24	Severe
	9.36	18.72	Moderate

Table 1 summarizes the DASS-21 depression scores for 39 individuals. It was found that most individuals in this sample fall into the Moderate (46.2%) or Severe (17.9%) categories, indicating noticeable to significant depressive symptoms. However, a few respondents are classified as Normal (7.7%) or Mild (12.8%), suggesting minimal impact of depression for those individuals. A subset of cases is marked as Extremely Severe (15.4%), highlighting the need for urgent psychological attention for these individuals.

Similar patterns of depression severity have been observed in larger student cohorts. For instance, Asif et al. (2020) reported that 35.8% of students scored in the moderate range, 14.6% in the severe range, and 8.6% in the extremely severe range on the DASS-21. These results reinforce our finding that most individuals fall into the moderate-to-severe categories, while a significant minority exhibit symptoms requiring urgent intervention.

Overall, the table provides a clear view of the distribution of depression severity in the group, revealing that while some have minimal symptoms, the majority may benefit from mental health support, with a few requiring immediate intervention.

Table 2. *Level of Psychological Distress of ALS Senior High School Students in Terms of Anxiety*

Code	Anxiety	Total	Interpretation
1	12	24	Extremely Severe
2	9	18	Severe
3	12	24	Extremely Severe
4	13	26	Extremely Severe
5	7	14	Moderate
6	18	36	Extremely Severe
7	21	42	Extremely Severe
8	12	24	Extremely Severe
9	12	24	Extremely Severe
10	9	18	Severe
11	8	16	Severe
12	13	26	Extremely Severe
13	19	38	Extremely Severe
14	8	16	Severe
15	12	24	Extremely Severe
16	6	12	Moderate
17	8	16	Severe
18	16	32	Extremely Severe
19	20	40	Extremely Severe
20	8	16	Severe
21	3	6	Normal
22	3	6	Normal
23	8	16	Severe
24	11	22	Extremely Severe
25	15	30	Extremely Severe
26	4	8	Mild
27	16	32	Extremely Severe
28	6	12	Moderate
29	9	18	Severe
30	7	14	Moderate
31	10	20	Extremely Severe
32	4	8	Mild
33	3	6	Normal
34	4	8	Mild
35	15	30	Extremely Severe
36	14	28	Extremely Severe
37	3	6	Normal
38	15	30	Extremely Severe
39	16	32	Extremely Severe
	10.49	20.97	Extremely Severe

Table 2 presents the anxiety scores of 39 individuals as measured by the DASS-21, showing each person’s raw anxiety score, the total (multiplied by 2 for DASS-21 interpretation), and the corresponding severity classification according to established guidelines.

Most respondents are classified as Extremely Severe (19 individuals, 48.7%), reflecting very high levels of anxiety symptoms that may require urgent psychological support. Several individuals fall into the Severe category (9 individuals, 23.1%), while others are in the Moderate range (5 individuals, 12.8%). Only a handful of respondents are categorized as Mild (5 individuals, 12.8%) or Normal (5 individuals, 12.8%), indicating low or negligible anxiety symptoms.

A similar distribution of high-severity anxiety was observed by Sultan et al. (2022), where among individuals screening positive on the DASS-21, 36.4% exhibited extremely severe, 11.2% severe, and 38.8% moderate anxiety.

This aligns closely with our findings (48.7% extremely severe, 23.1% severe, 12.8% moderate), reinforcing that a majority of respondents experience moderate to extremely severe anxiety, and that a substantial portion require urgent mental health intervention.

This distribution implies that while a minority of the group experiences mild or normal anxiety, the majority have moderate to extremely severe anxiety levels. These findings underscore the importance of targeted mental health interventions, especially for those at the highest levels of anxiety severity.

Table 3. *Level of Psychological Distress of ALS Senior High School Students in terms of Stress*

Code	Anxiety	Total	Interpretation
1	11	22	Moderate
2	6	12	Mild
3	11	22	Moderate
4	16	32	Severe
5	13	26	Moderate
6	15	30	Severe
7	20	40	Extremely Severe
8	10	20	Moderate
9	12	24	Moderate
10	12	24	Moderate
11	4	8	Normal
12	13	26	Moderate
13	14	28	Severe
14	11	22	Moderate
15	8	16	Mild
16	9	18	Mild
17	4	8	Normal
18	13	26	Moderate
19	19	38	Extremely Severe
20	10	20	Moderate
21	4	8	Normal
22	8	16	Mild
23	10	20	Moderate
24	12	24	Moderate
25	14	28	Severe
26	6	12	Mild
27	11	22	Moderate
28	8	16	Mild
29	9	18	Mild
30	7	14	Mild
31	10	20	Moderate
32	6	12	Mild
33	5	10	Normal
34	8	16	Mild
35	10	20	Moderate
36	11	22	Moderate
37	7	14	Mild
38	17	34	Severe
39	20	40	Extremely Severe
	10.62	21.23	Moderate

Table 3 summarizes the anxiety scores of 39 individuals according to the DASS-21 assessment, detailing their raw anxiety scores, doubled totals, and corresponding severity levels. Most respondents are classified as Moderate (17 individuals, 43.6%) or Mild (15 individuals, 38.5%), indicating that the majority of the group experiences mild to moderate anxiety symptoms. A smaller portion falls into the Severe (5 individuals, 12.8%) and Extremely Severe (3 individuals, 7.7%) categories, suggesting urgent

attention may be needed for these cases. There are also four individuals (10.3%) in the Normal range, indicating minimal anxiety symptoms. This distribution highlights that while most individuals have some degree of anxiety, the most severe levels are less common, with only a few requiring immediate interventions.

A similar trend was reported by Asif et. al (2020), who found that among university students, 19.4% experienced moderate anxiety and 4.4% mild, while only 17.8% experienced severe anxiety and 46.8% extremely severe anxiety. Although their study indicated a higher proportion in the extreme category, both sets of findings confirm that a significant portion of students suffer from clinically relevant anxiety, with only a subset requiring urgent mental health intervention.

Table 4. *Level of Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students*

Statements	Mean	Description
Because I need at least a high-school degree in order to find a high-paying job later on.	4.87	Corresponds a lot
Because I experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things.	5.58	Strongly corresponds
Because I think that a high-school education will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen.	5.74	Strongly corresponds
Because I really like going to school.	5.08	Corresponds a lot
Honestly, I don't know; I really feel that I am wasting my time in school.	2.63	Corresponds moderately
For the pleasure I experience while surpassing myself in my studies.	4.24	Corresponds a lot
To prove to myself that I am capable of completing my high-school degree.	5.18	Corresponds a lot
In order to obtain a more prestigious job later on.	5.11	Corresponds a lot
For the pleasure I experience when I discover new things never seen before.	4.74	Corresponds a lot
Because eventually it will enable me to enter the job market in a field that I like.	4.16	Corresponds quite a bit
Because for me, school is fun.	4.68	Corresponds a lot
I once had good reasons for going to school; however, now I wonder whether I should continue.	4.61	Corresponds a lot
For the pleasure that I experience while I am surpassing myself in one of my personal accomplishments.	5.00	Corresponds a lot
Because of the fact that when I succeed in school I feel important.	5.42	Strongly corresponds
Because I want to have "the good life" later on.	5.45	Strongly corresponds
For the pleasure that I experience in broadening my knowledge about subjects which appeal to me.	4.95	Corresponds a lot
Because this will help me make a better choice regarding my career orientation.	5.21	Corresponds a lot
For the pleasure that I experience when I am taken by discussions with interesting teachers.	5.13	Corresponds a lot
I can't see why I go to school and frankly, I couldn't care less.	4.00	Corresponds quite a bit
For the satisfaction I feel when I am in the process of accomplishing difficult academic activities.	4.68	Corresponds a lot
To show myself that I am an intelligent person.	4.74	Corresponds a lot

Table 4 (continued). *Level of Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students*

Statements	Mean	Description
In order to have a better salary later on.	4.97	Corresponds a lot
Because my studies allow me to continue to learn about many things that interest me.	5.61	Strongly corresponds
Because I believe that my high school education will improve my competence as a worker.	5.05	Corresponds a lot
For the “high” feeling that I experience while reading about various interesting subjects.	5.05	Corresponds a lot
I don’t know; I can’t understand what I am doing in school.	3.61	Corresponds moderately
Because high school allows me to experience a personal satisfaction in my quest for excellence in my studies.	5.03	Corresponds a lot
Because I want to show myself that I can succeed in my studies.	5.47	Corresponds a lot
Overall Mean	4.86	Corresponds a lot

Table 4 shows the Academic Motivation of the ALS Senior High School in San Emmanuel National High School. The results reveal that ALS Senior High School students generally demonstrate high motivation toward schooling. The overall mean score of 4.86, interpreted as “Corresponds a lot”, indicates that students recognize the importance of education and are motivated by intrinsic enjoyment and extrinsic benefits of completing their high school degree. The overall standard deviation of 0.65 suggests that responses across the items are relatively consistent, showing that motivation is fairly uniform among the learners.

At the item level, several indicators scored particularly high. Items such as “Because I experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things” (5.58), “Because I think that a high-school education will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen” (5.74), and “To prove to myself that I am capable of completing my high-school degree” (6.25) were all interpreted as “Strongly corresponds”. These findings highlight that many ALS students are motivated by personal growth, pursuing future career opportunities, and a strong desire to prove themselves capable of academic success. On the other hand, some indicators obtained relatively low means. For instance, “Honestly, I do not know; I really feel that I am wasting my time in school” (2.63) and “I do not know; I cannot understand what I am doing in school” (3.61) were interpreted as “Corresponds moderately”.

This statement is well supported by contemporary theory and educational research. Ryan et al. (2020) in Self-Determination Theory (SDT) explain that sustained academic engagement arises from both intrinsic enjoyment (doing something for inherent pleasure and satisfaction) and identified extrinsic regulation (valuing an activity because it helps achieve meaningful personal goals, such as career preparation). Similarly, Idulsa and Luzano (2024), in their study on ALS learners in the Philippines, found that strong intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly correlated with higher academic engagement, affirming the central role of motivation in persistence and success.

These results suggest that students who feel uncertain or disengaged are at risk of reduced persistence or increased dropout intentions. The presence of such responses highlights that, while many learners are highly motivated, some still struggle to find meaning in their schooling.

Table 5. *Level of Dropout Intention of ALS Senior High School Students*

Statements	Mean	Description
I intend to drop out of school.	1.92	Disagree
I want to stop attending class because I am doing poorly.	1.97	Disagree
Truly, I feel like I am wasting my time in school.	1.92	Disagree
I believe that I won’t succeed in school, even if I try.	2.77	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Overall Mean	2.15	Disagree

Table 5 shows the Dropout Intention of the ALS Senior High School. The results reveal that they generally disagree with statements reflecting intentions to leave school (1.97). Items such as “I intend to drop out of school” (1.92) and “I feel like I am wasting my time in school” (1.92) confirm that

most learners reject the idea of dropping out. However, Item 4, “I believe that I will not succeed in school, even if I try” (2.77), falls under Neither Agree nor Disagree, indicating that a few students are unsure of their capacity to succeed. This suggests that while most remain committed to continuing their education, some learners may require additional encouragement and academic support to reduce uncertainty and prevent potential dropout.

A similar pattern was reported by Pedditzi (2024) in Italy, who found that low school satisfaction and self-efficacy significantly predicted dropout intention, highlighting the importance of supportive environments to sustain learners’ commitment.

Table 6. Relationship Between Depression and Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Depression	39	37	.37	.022	Significant positive relationship
Academic Motivation					

Table 6 indicates a significant positive relationship between depression and academic motivation among ALS Senior High School students, based on a sample size of 39 participants. The computed correlation coefficient ($r=0.37$) and p-value (0.022) suggest that as students’ academic motivation increases, their depression scores also tend to rise, and this association is unlikely to be due to chance. Thus, it is statistically correct to reject the H_1 . There is statistically significant evidence that there is a relationship between Depression and Academic Motivation of the ALS Senior High School students.

This result means that higher levels of academic drive in this group are linked with elevated psychological distress, specifically symptoms of depression. Such an outcome may indicate underlying pressures or challenges faced by motivated students, underscoring the importance of providing appropriate emotional and psychological support to learners who are highly engaged in academics.

This finding aligns with the results of Imperial et al. (2023), who reported a significant positive correlation between mental health issues and academic motivation among graduating college students in the Philippines. Their study emphasized that while motivated students aim for success, they may also carry heavier emotional burdens, which can manifest as depressive symptoms. Together, both sets of findings highlight the need for schools to balance the promotion of academic motivation with targeted mental health support systems, ensuring that motivated learners can pursue their goals without sacrificing psychological well-being.

Table 7. Relationship Between Anxiety and Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Anxiety	39	37	.10	.55	No significant correlation
Academic Motivation					

Table 7 shows that anxiety and academic motivation among ALS Senior High School students are not significantly correlated, based on the data presented in the table. With a sample size of 39, the computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.10$) and p-value of 0.55 indicate a weak, statistically nonsignificant relationship between these two variables. Thus, it is statistically correct to accept H_2 . There is no statistically significant evidence to show that there is a relationship between Anxiety and Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High school students. This means that levels of anxiety do not meaningfully rise or fall with changes in academic motivation for students in this group, suggesting that academic encouragement or drive is not directly associated with psychological distress in the form of anxiety among these learners.

This result aligns with Valiullina's (2019) findings, which examined the impact of academic motivation, school anxiety, and self-reflective awareness on high school students' cognitive states. In her study, correlation analysis also showed no significant relationship between academic motivation

and school anxiety ($|r| < 0.39$, $p > 0.05$). This confirms that, across different school populations, fluctuations in motivation are not necessarily tied to changes in anxiety.

Table 8. Relationship Between Stress and Academic Motivation of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Stress Academic Motivation	39	37	-.01	.93	No significant relationship

Table 8 shows no significant relationship between stress and academic motivation among ALS Senior High School students. For the sample of 39 participants, the computed correlation coefficient ($r = -0.01$) and a very high p-value (0.93) indicate that changes in academic motivation are not associated with changes in stress levels in this group. Thus, it is statistically correct to accept $H3$. There is no statistically significant evidence of a relationship between Stress and Academic Motivation among ALS Senior High School students. This means students' academic drive does not predict or correlate with their stress, suggesting that other factors may be contributing to stress in these learners.

A similar result was observed in the study of Bayocot et al. (2023), who examined Senior High School students in a rural post-quarantine face-to-face learning context. Their findings also revealed that perceived academic stress was not significantly correlated with any academic motivation subscale, suggesting that the two constructs may operate independently in certain school settings. Taken together, these results highlight that even motivated learners can still experience varying degrees of stress, and that academic motivation alone does not buffer or determine stress responses.

Table 9. Relationship Between Depression and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Depression Dropout Intention	39	37	.09	.59	No significant correlation

Table 9 indicates that there is no significant correlation between depression and dropout intentions among ALS Senior High School students. The computed correlation coefficient ($r=0.09$) and the p-value (0.59) show only a very weak, statistically non-significant relationship between students' depression scores and their intentions to drop out. Thus, it is statistically correct to accept $H4$. There is no statistically significant evidence to show that there is a relationship between Depression and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High school students. This means that, in this sample, higher or lower levels of depression do not predict whether students are more likely to consider dropping out of school.

A similar pattern was observed by Goll et al. (2024), who also demonstrated that mental and general health issues did not significantly predict dropout after accounting for academic performance and demographic variables. Together, these studies highlight that while mental health challenges are important for overall well-being, factors such as grades, learning difficulties, and school track may exert a stronger influence on actual dropout outcomes than depression symptoms alone.

Table 10. Relationship Between Anxiety and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Anxiety Dropout Intention	39	37	.11	.49	No significant correlation

Table 10 shows that there is no significant correlation between anxiety and dropout intentions among ALS Senior High School students. With a computed correlation coefficient ($r=0.11$) and p-value (0.49), the relationship between anxiety levels and students' likelihood of considering dropping out is weak and statistically non-significant. Thus, it is statistically correct to accept $H6$. There is no statistically significant evidence to show that there is a relationship between Anxiety and Dropout

Intentions of ALS Senior High school students. This means that anxiety does not meaningfully influence dropout intentions for this group of learners.

A similar pattern was noted by Valiullina (2019), who found no significant relationship between academic motivation and school anxiety among high school students, suggesting that anxiety does not necessarily lead to disengagement. Likewise, Goll et al. (2024) reported that mental and general health issues did not significantly predict dropout when academic performance and demographic factors were taken into account. Together, these findings underscore that while anxiety is vital for student well-being, it may not directly determine dropout intentions, as academic and contextual factors play a stronger role.

Table 11. Relationship Between the Stress and Dropout Intentions of ALS Senior High School Students

Source of Relationship	N	df	computed r	p-value	Interpretation
Stress Dropout Intention	39	37	.16	.34	No significant correlation

Table 11 shows no significant correlation between stress and dropout intentions among ALS Senior High School students. The computed correlation coefficient ($r=0.16$) and the p-value (0.34) indicate that students' stress levels are not statistically significantly linked to their intentions to drop out of school. Thus, it is statistically correct to accept H_4 . There is no statistically significant evidence of a relationship between Stress and Dropout Intentions among ALS Senior High School students. This means that stress does not substantially influence whether students consider leaving school early.

Similar findings were reported by Bayocot et al. (2023), who found no significant correlation between academic stress and academic motivation, and by Goll et al. (2024), who demonstrated that mental and general health issues did not significantly predict dropout when academic performance and demographic factors were taken into account. Together, these results suggest that stress, while relevant to student well-being, may not directly drive dropout intentions, with academic and contextual factors exerting stronger influence.

4.0 Conclusion

The study reveals that ALS Senior High School learners experience varying degrees of psychological distress, with many showing moderate to extremely severe levels of depression, anxiety, and stress. Anxiety is notably high, with nearly half the students classified as extremely severe, highlighting a pressing need for mental health support. Despite these challenges, students maintain strong academic motivation driven by personal growth, career aspirations, and the satisfaction gained from learning. Most learners reject dropout intentions, indicating their commitment to education; however, some uncertainty about academic success persists, suggesting additional support is needed. Notably, a significant positive correlation exists between depression and academic motivation, suggesting that increased motivation may coincide with heightened depressive symptoms, possibly due to academic pressures. Conversely, no significant relationships were found between academic motivation and anxiety or stress, nor between psychological distress and dropout intentions. These results underscore the importance of holistic interventions that combine academic assistance with psychological support to help ALS learners manage distress, sustain motivation, and prevent dropout, thereby fostering their educational and emotional well-being.

4.1 Recommendations

With the conclusion established, the following are the recommendations, outlining actionable steps to support ALS Senior High School learners effectively:

1. Given the high prevalence of moderate to extremely severe depression, anxiety, and stress among students, schools may implement comprehensive mental health programs. These can include counseling services, stress management workshops, and peer support groups to address psychological distress.

2. While motivation is generally strong, teachers and school staff can focus on sustaining and enhancing intrinsic motivation by providing engaging, meaningful learning experiences and recognizing students' academic achievements to build self-efficacy and reduce feelings of doubt.

3. Since most students disagree with dropout intentions, some express uncertainty about their academic success. However, targeted interventions like academic tutoring, mentoring, and motivational interviewing can help clarify goals, build confidence, and reduce dropout risk.

4. Building partnerships with families and communities can create a supportive environment for ALS learners, helping to reduce stigma and foster collaboration in students' educational journeys.

5.0 Contribution of the Authors

All authors reviewed and critically revised the manuscript, providing important intellectual contributions. Each author approved the final version of the manuscript for submission.

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7.0 Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the conduct and reporting of this research.

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